

Synthetic Studies in the Diterpene Series*

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It is indeed a great honour and privilege to me to be called upon to deliver the Basudev Banerjee Memorial Lecture before you to celebrate the birth anniversary of late Dr. Basudev Banerjee. But before I do so, I must take this opportunity to pay my respectful tributes to the departed soul. On the few occasions I had the privilege to meet him, I was struck by his genial temper, honesty and steadfastness of purpose, and a robust optimism towards research. Such qualities go to make a truly great scientist. It is very unfortunate that he was removed from our midst so prematurely by a cruel decree of fate. I would also like to express my sincere thanks to the Indian Chemical Society for giving me this opportunity to present the humble contribution from our laboratory on such a memorial occasion.

The present work is a part of a series of investigations on the synthesis of diterpenoids and related compounds, carried out by the speaker singly and in collaboration of his research associates since 1957 in the Department of Pure Chemistry, University Colleges of Science and Technology, Calcutta. The idea was to work out a simple route to podocarpa-8, 11, 13-triene ring system (I) and to employ it for the synthesis of a few naturally occurring phenolic diterpenes, starting with materials readily available to us and using methods accessible to our very limited laboratory facilities. The object, as will be seen by the sequel, has been achieved, though I am doubtful whether this synthetic rigmarole will have much intellectual appeal to you, coming as it does, at a time when such complex molecular architectures as of chlorophyll, strychnine, reserpine, longifoline, to mention only a few, have already yielded to the synthetic ingenuity of the organic chemists.

Of the various tricyclic diterpenes, the phenolic derivatives, commonly known as resinols, offer comparatively easy target to the synthetic chemists for their relatively simple stereochemistry. These resinols comprise three important members, ferruginol, totarol, and podocarpic acid and their derivatives (Chart I) with additional oxygen function either at C₃ or C₇ and occasionally with one of the *gem*-dimethyl group in different states of oxidation (*e.g.*, CO₂H, CHO, or CH₂OH). The latest addition to this group of diterpenes is nimbiol isolated from *Melia azadirachta* by two Indian workers. With the inclusion of dehydroabietic acid, which does not occur in nature but is derived from abietic acid, the list of aromatic diterpenes is almost complete.

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In spite of the comparative simplicity of the molecules, the first authenticated synthesis of a member of these series, namely ($\pm$)-ferruginol, was, however, reported¹² only in 1954.

CHART I

Prior to the commencement of our present investigation, two methods were available for the synthesis of this type of compounds. In the first method, the Grignard reagents of appropriate phenethyl halides or preferably the potassio-derivative of the corresponding phenylacetylenes (III) were condensed with tri-substituted cyclohexanones (II) (Chart II) and the saturated cyclohexanols (IV), obtained directly or after catalytic reduction, cyclodehydrated to the podocarpatriene derivatives (V). The procedure, first initiated

1. Fteroid Nomenclature: Fieser and Fieser, "Natural Products Related to Phenanthrene", 1949, p. 92.
2. Brandt and Neubauer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1031.
3. Easterfield and McDowel, *Trans. New Zealand Inst.*, 1911, 43, 55; 1916, 48, 518.
4. Oudmans, *Ber.*, 1873, 6, 1122, 1125; *Annalen*, 1873, 170, 214; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1874, 9, 395; Easterfield and Aston, *Trans. New Zealand Inst.*, 1910, 42, 53; 1911, 43, 53.
5. Keimatsu et al., *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1937, 57, 92; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1937, 11, 506; Sengupta et al., *Chem. & Ind.*, 1958, 961.
6. Bredenberg and Gripenberg, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1950, 10, 1511; Briggs et al., *Tetrahedron*, 1959, 7, 270; Kondo et al., *Bull. Agr. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1959, 23, 233.
7. Yoshiki and Ishiguro, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1933, 53, 11; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1933, I, 3205.
8. Chow and Erdtmann, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1960, 14, 1852.
9. Hodges, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4247.
10. Taylor, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, 1712.
11. Sengupta et al., *Tetrahedron*, 1960, 10, 45.
12. Fieser and Campbell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 159.
13. King et al., *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 108; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 573.

by Haworth and Moore¹⁴ and also by Bhattacharya¹⁵, has been successfully used by King *et al.*¹³ for the synthesis of ($\pm$)-ferruginol and later by Barltrop and Rogers¹⁶ for the synthesis of ($\pm$)-totarol, the introduction of the isopropyl group in each case being effected at a later stage by a series of further reactions. A few analogous syntheses, differing only in the method of preparation of the cyclohexanol derivatives, are also known¹⁷.

CHART II

The drawback of these syntheses is their complete lack of steric control, the product requiring laborious process of separation of the stereoisomers. The second method, which is a definite improvement on this point, consists in the Robinson-Mannich base ring extension of substituted β -tetralones (VI), methylation of the resultant unsaturated ketone (VII), reduction of the carbonyl function, and finally stereospecific hydrogenation of the double bond leading to ($\pm$)-5 α -podocarpatriene derivative (X). The procedure has been used for a synthesis of ($\pm$)-ferruginol by Raman and Rao¹⁸ and with important modification for the synthesis of dehydroabietic acid by Stork and Schulenberg¹⁹, and also lately by quite a number of other workers²⁰. Besides being stereospecific, the method provides a route to 3-oxygenated phenolic diterpenes *via* the ketone (VIII), *e.g.*, hinokione²¹ and 3-oxototarol²².

14. Haworth and Moore, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 633.

15. Bhattacharya, *this Journal*, 1945, 22, 165.

16. Barltrop and Rogers, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1957, 997; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2566.

17. Ghatak *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 1728; Sharma, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, 23, 1.

18. Raman and Rao, *Exper.*, 1956, 473; *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 4, 294.

19. Stork and Schulenberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 250; 1962, 84, 284.

20. Elmore and King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4426; Ramchandran and Dutta, *ibid.*, 1960, 4768.

21. Chow, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1962, 16, 1301.

22. Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3819.

We started with the idea that an appropriately substituted diene of the type (XI) might undergo an acid-catalysed cyclisation with the formation of the podocarpa-8, 11, 13-trione system in a single step. Moreover, the process might very well be synchronous, the nucleophilic attack of the aromatic ring to the centrally situated double bond being

CHART III

CHART IV

assisted by the electrophilic attack of the proton from the other end of the chain, as shown (Chart IV). The consequence of such a concerted mechanism²³ is the formation of an octahydrophenanthrene system (XII) with the desired *trans* A/B ring fusion. Though the dienes (XI) themselves are not readily available, the ω -arylalkanoates of the type (XIII and XIV), which may serve as potential dienes under the condition of reaction, can be easily prepared. Thus condensation of γ -phenylpropylmagnesium bromide and methylheptanone²⁴ afforded in a single step and in excellent yield 4,8-dimethyl-1-phenylnon-7-*on*-4-ol (XV), whereas methyl 5-oxo-8-phenyloctanoate (XVI), prepared from ethyl β -oxopimelate²⁵ and phenethyl bromide by successive alkylation, hydrolysis, and esterification, afforded 2,6-dimethyl-9-phenylnonane-2,6-diol (XVII) on treatment with methylmagnesium iodide. These alcohols (XV and XVII) on cyclodehydration with polyphosphoric acid indeed provided the podocarpa-8,11,13-triene (I)²⁶ in an excellent yield, identified by ultraviolet absorption spectra²⁷ and conversion to 1-methylphenanthrene²⁸. The feasibility of the double cyclisation of the alcohols (XV and XVII) in the desired direction was thus definitely established.

CHART V

Before applying this method to the synthesis of naturally occurring diterpenes, two aspects of this cyclisation must, however, be studied, namely, the stereochemistry of the product and the effect of substituents in the aromatic ring on the course of cyclisation. At this time, Wenkert and Jackson²⁹ made a very significant observation that octahydrophenanthrene derivatives of the type (XII) on controlled oxidation with chromic acid in aqueous acetic acid provided two major products, depending on the nature of the A/B ring junction—*a* monoketone (XVIII) from the *trans*-isomer and *a* diketone (XIX) from

23. Stork and Burgstahler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5068.

24. Verley, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1897, **iii**, 17, 175.

25. Guha *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1930, **37**, 287.

26. Nasipuri, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1957, 425.

27. Aakew, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 512.

28. Haworth, *ibid.*, 1932, 1125.

29. Wenkert and Jackson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 211.

the *cis*-isomer, these ketones being easily separable by chromatography. This oxidation has since then been used as a diagnostic method for the determination of the stereochemistry of such a ring system. The work in our laboratory at this stage was, however, interrupted, the speaker being away on a foreign mission. Meanwhile, Fetizon and co-workers adopted our procedure and synthesised 12-methoxy-³⁰ (XXII) and 14-methoxy-podocarpatrienes³¹ (XX), the former being subsequently converted into ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether³² (XXV) (Chart V) and the latter reduced to the perhydropheanthrene ketone (XXI), a valuable synthetic intermediate for the phyllocladane group of diterpenes³³.

CHART VI

Fetizon and co-workers³² also established the stereochemistry of the cyclised product by oxidation and separation of the ketonic fragments (XVIII and XIX) and then by an independent unambiguous synthesis of these two. Some of their experimental results overlapped with ours and we had to abandon any further experimentation in this direction. One thing, however, became quite clear by this time that the double cyclisation was by no means stereospecific, as envisaged before, but led to a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers, the latter predominating in most of the cases. The lack of stereospecificity is fortunately recompen-sated to a great extent by the application of the *Wenkert* oxidation, allowing preparation and separation of any or both isomers in a series of ketones. The success of the method being thus assured, we next intended to employ this for the synthesis of a few members of the ferruginol and totarol groups of

30. Delobelle and Fetizon, *Compt. rend.*, 1958, 246, 2774.

31. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1960, 251, 2048.

32. Fetizon and Delobelle, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, 8, 16.

33. Turner and Shaw, *ibid.*, 1961, 7, 231.

34. Fetizon and Delobelle, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1961, 1632.

diterpenes and also for an alternative synthesis of nimbiol. Preparations of the different substituted phenethyl and phenylpropyl alcohols, required for these syntheses, are shown schematically in Chart VI and need little explanation. The condensation of isopropyl alcohol with *p*-bromoanisole providing 4-bromo-3-isopropylanisole in high yield (80%) is rather fortunate, as it simplifies the preparation of the alcohols (XXVI and XXVII). The very interesting reaction of 2,3-dimethoxybenzotrile with isopropylmagnesium iodide, in which the central methoxyl is replaced by isopropyl group³⁵, has been taken advantage of for the preparation of the alcohols (XXVIII and XXIX). As far as we know, these alcohols have not been reported in the literature.

CHART VII

Once the proper phenethyl and phenylpropyl alcohols were available, the synthesis of the desired diterpenes became really very simple. Thus, condensation of 3-(3-isopropyl-4-methoxyphenyl)propylmagnesium bromide with methylheptenone afforded the unsaturated alcohol (XXXII) and the condensation of 3-isopropyl-4-methoxyphenethyl bromide with ethyl β -oxopimelate and subsequent reactions afforded the diol (XXXIII) in good yield. Cyclodehydration of the both furnished a stereoisomeric mixture of ($\pm$)-13-isopropyl-12-methoxypodocarpa-8, 11,13-triene (XXXIV), which was oxidized by chromic acid in acetic acid, and the product was resolved by chromatography into three ketonic fractions (Chart VII)³⁶. The major fraction, m.p. 125-27°, was identified as ($\pm$)-sugyl methyl ether, the minor fraction as the methyl ether (XXXVI) of xanthoperol, m.p. 205°, and the third component, which was isolated in traces only, as 1,4-di-(3-isopropylanisoyl)butane (XXXVII), m.p. 146°, presumably formed by oxidation of 1,6-di-(3'-isopropyl-4'-methoxyphenyl)hexane, a byproduct of the preceding Grignard reaction. Identity of the synthetic compounds with those obtained from natural sources was established by comparison of ul-

*Only one enantiomer is shown.

35. Fuson *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, 13, 489; Richtzenhain and Nippus, *Ber.*, 1944, 77, 586.
36. Nasipuri and Guha, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4248.

traviolet and infrared absorption spectra. The methyl ether of (+)-xanthoperol was prepared from a specimen of the phenol, m. p. 255-70°, kindly donated by Dr. Bredenberg, and had m. p. 190-92° (λ_{max} 225, 250, and 349 m μ ; log ϵ , 3.95, 3.78, and 4.01 respectively).

CHART VIII

This records the first direct synthesis of ($\pm$)-sugiol and ($\pm$)-xanthoperol methyl ethers. (+)-Xanthoperol has only recently been isolated from *Juniperus communis* L, as an artifact and has been assigned the *cis*-6,7-dioxoferruginol structure from n. m. r. and other data³⁷. The present synthesis confirms this structure and also supports the natural 5 α -configuration assigned to its precursor³⁸.

37. Bredenberg and Shoolery, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1960, 14, 556.

38. Bredenberg, *ibid.*, 1960, 14, 385.

With the availability of the above phenethyl alcohols it also became possible to synthesise for the first time a number of phenanthrene and hydrophenanthrene derivatives (XXXVII—XLIV) which were obtained by complete or partial dehydrogenation of totarol³⁹, ferruginol^{40c}, sugiol^{40b}, hinokiol^{40c}, and nimbiol¹¹ and aided in elucidating the structures of these diterpenes in the earlier stages. The phenanthrenes (XL, XLI, and XLIV) were synthesised⁴¹ by successive alkylation of ethyl β -oxopimelate with phenethyl bromides, cyclodehydration of the resultant β -oxo-esters, and Dieckmann condensation, followed by conventional procedure. The tetrahydrophenanthrenes (XXXVIII, XXXIX, XLII, and XLIII) were synthesised by cyclodehydration of the naphthalene derivatives (XLVIII) which in turn were prepared either from the δ -oxo-esters (XLV) through cyclodehydration, dehydrogenation, and treatment with methylmagnesium iodide, or better from the α -tetralones (XLVI) by the action of methyl γ -bromocrotonate, followed by disproportionation⁴² of the product to the naphthalene ester (XLVII) and subsequent Grignard reaction with methylmagnesium iodide. The products in all cases compared well with those derived from natural sources. It may be relevant to mention in this connection the synthesis of two other hydrocarbons⁴³ (XLIX and LI), derived from isomeric dextropimaric acids⁴⁴ and also from a number of related natural products⁴⁵. The former (XLIX) was prepared from the tetrahydrophenanthrene ketone (L) by methylation and reduction and the latter (LI) from $\beta\beta$ -dimethylvaleronitrile (LII) by the action of δ -methyl-1-naphthylmagnesium bromide, followed by reduction of the carbonyl group.

We next attempted a synthesis of ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether (XXV) from the alcohols (LIII and LIV), almost as a routine measure, and obtained a very unexpected result. In a previous synthesis by Fetizon and Delobelle³², which appeared as a short note, the methyl group was introduced at a later stage by chloromethylation and reduction. In the subsequent paper⁴⁷ (1961), they reported their failure to cyclise the unsaturated alcohol (LIII) to deoxonimbiol skeleton. Our experimental results, which were published⁴⁶ a few months after, independently and without any prior knowledge of the failure of the French workers, though similar in essence, differed in some significant points and are discussed here. The product on cyclisation of the alcohols (LIII and LIV) showed no detectable amount of unsaturation towards catalytic hydrogenation and its ultraviolet absorption spectra ($\lambda_{\max}$ 279 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$, 3.34) were consistent broadly with the structure (LV). Chromic acid oxidation under the usual condition afforded a mixture of ketones, separated into several fragments by chromatography over alumina. The monoketonic fraction after prolonged keeping at 0° in contact with methanol afforded crystals, m.p. 112–14°, in minute yield (dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 232°) which contrary to the observation of Delobelle and Fetizon⁴⁷ were found to be identical in all respects with ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether⁴⁸. The rest of the monoketone

39. Short and Wang, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2979.

40. Simonsen, "The Terpenes", 1952, III, (a) p. 355, (b) p. 950, (c) p. 365.

41. Nasipuri and Chaudhuri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2579.

42. Cook and Schoental, *ibid.*, 1945, 288.

43. Nasipuri and Chaudhuri, *ibid.*, 1958, 4299.

44. Harris and Sanderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2081.

45. Briggs *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1958, 599; Galik *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1950, 7, 223.

46. Nasipuri and Roy, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1963, 21B, 50.

47. Delobelle and Fetizon, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1961, 1900.

48. Nasipuri and Roy, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 327.

(liquid; dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 271°), which consisted of almost 90% of the oxidised product, could not be identified at that time. Two diketones were also isolated in minute yields, one recognised as 1,4-dianisoylbutane derivative, m.p. 183°, from previous analogy and the other as the *cis*-diketone, m. p. 200° (LVI), the structure of the latter being confirmed by an unambiguous synthesis (*vide infra*). It seems quite clear therefore that with the alcohols (LIII and LIV), the normal cyclisation takes place only to a very small extent. With the data at our hand, we could speculate on three alternative structures (LVII, LIX, and LX) for the major cyclised product. The structure (LVII) is very unlikely as it involves cyclisation at a point *ortho* to a methyl group in preference to *para* in the benzene ring, although it seems to be consistent with the spectroscopic inference of Delobelle and Fetizon⁴⁷ that the cyclised product contains two vicinal hydrogen atoms in ring C. Such a structure (LVII) was, however, completely ruled out by the normal cyclisation (*para* to methyl) of the cyclohexanol (LXIII) to the podocarpatriene derivative (LV) which was subsequently oxidised to provide a mixture of ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether (XXV), m.p. 112-14°, and ($\pm$)-*cis*-6-oxonimbiol methyl ether (LVI), m.p. 200°.

CHART IX

The cyclohexanol (LXIII) was prepared by condensing 4-methoxy-3-methylbenzaldehyde with methyl isopropyl ketone, then submitting the resultant α - β -unsaturated ketone (LXI) to the Robinson-Mannich base synthesis with the help of 1-*N*-diethylaminopentan-3-one⁴⁹ methiodide, and reducing the trimethylcyclohexenone derivative (LXII) successively with hydrogen in presence of palladium-charcoal and lithium aluminium hydride,

following a procedure of Church *et al.*⁵⁰. This leaves us with the other two alternative structures (LIX and LX) for the main cyclised product (henceforth to be called isodecaxonimbiol methyl ether), the formation of either of them being explained by a two-stage cyclisation with the tetralin derivative (LVIII) as an intermediate. The substituents in the benzene ring were found for the first time to have a profound effect on the course of cyclisation.

CHART X

In order to study the effect of substituents further and to elucidate the structure of the alternative cyclised product, 1-3'-methoxyphenyl-4,8-dimethylnon-7-en-4-ol (LXIV) and the corresponding diol (LXV) (Chart X) were next cyclised. The liquid product is completely different from 5- α -($\pm$)-13-methoxypodocarpatriene (LXVI), which is a crystalline solid^{50a}, m. p. 86-88°. The compound, moreover, exhibited a very unusual behaviour towards chromic acid oxidation, since it afforded a hydroxy- α - β -unsaturated ketone, m. p. 158°, instead of the usual aromatic ketone expected from the oxidation of benzylmethylene group. This non-aromatic ketone was found to have the *p*-quinol structure (LXVIII) on the basis of the following evidence⁵¹:

(a) Elemental analyses and molecular weight corresponds closely to the formula $C_{17}H_{24}O_4$, calculated for the structure (LXVIII). It has no methoxyl group and forms a low-melting dinitrophenylhydrazone (red), m. p. 124°.

(b) The infrared spectrum shows a peak at 3630 cm^{-1} due to free hydroxyl and a doublet at 1663 and 1623 cm^{-1} , attributable to a 1,4-diene-3-ketonic system⁵², the other details being consistent with the structure (LXVIII).

(c) The ultraviolet absorption spectrum (λ_{max} 246 $\text{m}\mu$; $\log \epsilon$, 4.32) is characteristic of an α - β -unsaturated ketone and fits nicely to the structure (LXVIII). The substituted

50. (a) Church *et al.*; *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1980, 17, 1; also (b) Akita and Weedon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 4058, 51. Nasipuri and Pyne, in Press.

52. Fieser and Fieser, "Steroids", Asia Publishing House, 1960, p. 170.

m-anisoyl derivative, e.g., 7-oxototarol methyl ether, on the other hand, have a quite different type of spectra (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1

(d) Finally, the nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum (Fig. 2) provided a very convincing proof for the structure (LXVIII). It showed a sharp singlet at 7.37 τ corresponding in area to one proton (OH), two overlapping doublets, one centred at 9.07 τ and

FIG. 2

other at 9.18 τ ($J=10$ c.p.s; CHMe_2) and a sharp singlet at 9.27 τ (an unsplit $-\text{CH}_3$), the area of the last three bands corresponding exactly to nine protons. Besides, it showed a

53. Bhacca, Johnson, and Shooley, "NMR Spectra Catalog", Varian Associates, 1962, Spectrum No. (a) 345, (b) 275, and (c) 271.

band at 4.06 τ (area, 2) indicating the presence of two α -protons on an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl system as in 19-norprogesterone (4.13 τ)^{53a} and piperitone (4.13 τ)^{53b}. A β -proton in such a system, on the other hand, would absorb much further downfield (cf. carvone, 3.25 τ)^{53c}. All other protons were lost in a vague shapeless mound round about 8 τ . On the whole, it presents a most self-consistent and satisfactory picture.

The original cyclised product must therefore be represented as a hydrophenalene derivative (LXVII). This was also corroborated by its nuclear magnetic resonance data (Fig. 3) of which the peaks at 3.44 and 3.56 τ (two aromatic protons) and at 8.91, 9.08, 9.12, and 9.24 τ (isopropyl) are noteworthy.

FIG 3

FIG. 4

Similar results were also obtained in an attempt to synthesise ($\pm$)-totaryl methyl ether, the unsaturated alcohol (LXIX) and its diol analogue were cyclodehydrated. Here the product, which we name isototaryl methyl ether (LXX), is a crystalline solid, m. p. 84°, affording on chromic acid oxidation the *p*-quinol (LXXI), m. p. 168° (dini-

trophenylhydrazone, m. p. 145-46°). The structures of both these compounds were confirmed by the nuclear magnetic resonance data (Figs. 4 and 5) and also by the ultraviolet and infrared absorption spectra.

FIG. 5

In the light of the above experiments, isodeoxonimbiol methyl ether, previously encountered by us, looked almost certainly to be another hydrophenalene derivative (LIX), as indeed proved by an unambiguous synthesis (Chart XI)⁵⁴.

CHART XI

Methyl 8-(4'-methoxy-3'-methylphenyl)-5-oxooctanoate (LXXII) on treatment with a molar proportion of methylmagnesium iodide furnished the hydroxy-ester (LXXIII).

⁵⁴ Nasipuri and Roy, in press.

The latter was cyclodehydrated by 90% sulphuric acid and the resultant tetralin was hydrolysed to provide γ -1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1,6-dimethyl-7-methoxy-1-naphthylbutyric acid (LXXIV), m. p. 114-15° (structure confirmed by its n. m. r. spectrum). The derived methyl ester was treated with an excess of methylmagnesium iodide and the product cyclised by polyphosphoric acid to the hydrophenalene derivative (LIX). This was oxidised by chromic acid to furnish a liquid ketone (LXXVI), found to be identical with isonimbiol methyl ether by superimposable ultraviolet absorption spectra ($\lambda_{\max}$ 275 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$, 4.08) and by comparison of the dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m. p. and mixed m. p. 271°. It may be interesting to note that the compound (LIX) underwent normal oxidation to the aromatic ketone (LXXVI), as indicated by the presence of a methoxyl group in the molecule and by its ultraviolet absorption spectra.

The effect of the substituents in the phenyl ring in directing the course of the above cyclisation certainly calls for an explanation. An inspection of the different unsaturated alcohols (and also the corresponding diols) and their cyclisation products reveals one very interesting fact, namely, those alcohols (e.g., XV, LXXVII, LXXVIII, and XXXII; 1st row compounds, Chart XII), in which the nucleophilic activity of the aromatic ring is not very much pronounced at the reaction site, undergo cyclisation to afford podocarprione derivatives (XII), whereas the rest (LXIV, LXIX, and LIII; 2nd row compounds, Chart XII), where the phenyl groups are specially activated either by methoxyl groups at appropriate positions or by methyl-hyperconjugation in conjunction with a *m*-methoxyl group as in compound (LIII), undergo cyclisation to provide hydrophenalenes (LXXXII).

CHART XII

A rational explanation may be offered on the basis of the following mechanism. The first step in the reaction is obviously the formation of the carbonium ion (LXXXIX)

which can competitively (a) undergo a β -proton elimination, giving rise to the diene (LXXX) and ending up mostly to the podocarpatriene derivative (XII) either by a concerted or more probably by a non-concerted* mechanism, or (b) succumb to the nucleophilic attack of the aromatic ring, leading first to the tetralins (LXXXI) and thence to the hydrophenalenes (LXXXII). The low nucleophilicity of the aromatic system in the unsaturated alcohols, grouped in the upper row of Chart XII, allows the cyclisation to proceed *via* the intermediate diene (LXXX) (route 'a'), whereas the greater nucleophilic activity of the carbonium ion leading to the tetralin derivatives (LXXXI) (route 'b') and thence to the hydrophenalenes (LXXXII). The mechanism also explains the formation of ($\pm$)-ferruginol methyl ether³⁶ as a major product of cyclisation of the alcohols (XXXII and XXXIII), where the replacement of methyl by isopropyl group makes hyperconjugation almost negligible. The effect of hyperconjugation is thus very strikingly demonstrated in these experiments.

In order to have supporting evidence for the mechanism, the unsaturated alcohol (LXIV) was dehydrated with anhydrous copper sulphate and the resultant mixture of 3,7- and 4,7-dienes (LXXXIII and LXXXIV) cyclised under the usual conditions. Careful chromatography over alumina indeed afforded crystalline 5 α -($\pm$)-13-methoxy-podocarpa-8,11,13-triene (LXVI), m.p. and mixed† m.p. 86-88°, though in a very poor yield (5%). The low yield of the expected podocarpatriene can be accounted on the ground that the dehydration leads to a mixture of dienes of which only one (LXXXIV) would afford the right product, whereas the whole of the isomeric 4,7-diene (LXXXIII) and possibly a good part of the 3,7-diene (LXXXIV) would undergo protonation and be cyclised to the hydrophenalene structure (LXXXII) *via* the intermediate carbonium ion (LXXIX). The liquid fraction after separation of 5 α -($\pm$)-13-methoxy-podocarpatriene (LXVI) on chromic acid oxidation furnished, in fact, an appreciable amount of the *p*-quinol (LXVIII).

CHART XIII

Finally, the oxidation of the methoxyhydrophenalenes of the type (LXVII) to *p*-quinols (LXVIII) requires some comment. This is indeed a very unique observation. Recently quite a number of monoalkyl and monoaryl ethers of catechol and hydroquinones and also a few polyalkylphenols have been oxidised by Adler *et al.*³⁵ (Chart XIV)

*A non-concerted mechanism is to be preferred since a purely concerted cyclisation according to Stork and Burgstahler³³ would lead to the *trans*-(5 α)-isomer exclusively.

†An authentic sample was prepared according to the procedure of Church *et al.*³⁰.

³⁵ Adler *et al.*, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, 13, 505; 1960, 14, 512, 1261; 1962, 16, 529; Goodwin and Witkop, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 179.

with sodium periodate, but in all these cases the oxidation has been supposed to be initiated at the phenolic group. In the present cases, the electrophilic species of the oxidising agent evidently attacks the aromatic ring at the site of the greatest electron density, namely, *para* to the methoxyl group, and subsequent changes follow.

CHART XIV

CHART XV

The gross mechanism is shown in Chart XV. It is interesting to know whether this oxidation is characteristic of the system (LXVIIa) only or more general. Isoeoxonimbiol methyl ether with the methoxyl at C₆ has already been shown to be oxidised at C₃. A model compound, 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-6-methoxy-1,1-dimethylnaphthalene (LXXXV) underwent normal oxidation to 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-6-methoxy-1,1-dimethyl-4-oxonaphthalene⁵⁶ at our hand, whereas a heterocyclic derivative (LXXXVI) was recently oxidised by the Japanese workers⁵⁷ to 7-oxo-derivative under identical condition.

56. Mukherjee, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19B, 94.

57. Iwai *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1962, 1288.

A preliminary oxidation of 5 α -($\pm$)-13-methoxypodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (LXVI), on the other hand, appeared to furnish an abnormal product which is being investigated. Oxidation of a few more analogous cases is also being examined by us which may throw further light on this problem.

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